

NATIONAL HARMONY AND PEACE - A FACTOR OF PROGRESS AND PROSPERITY

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It is known that the territory of Central Asia, in particular, Uzbekistan, has been a region since ancient times where many diverse peoples live, professing different religions, having different cultures, languages, customs, lifestyle. The location of the territory of Uzbekistan at the intersection of important trade routes from a geographical point of view, the economic ties of the kingdoms on this land with many states have had a significant impact on the religious and spiritual life of indigenous peoples, and the traditions of Transoxiana - on the development of the culture of other countries. This was one of the main factors in the formation of interethnic solidarity and religious tolerance.

Islam and other religions have coexisted and developed on the territory of Uzbekistan since ancient times. This has made a certain contribution to the spiritual uplift of society. Currently, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and nationalities live in our country. Since the first days of independence, Uzbekistan has identified interethnic and interfaith tolerance and harmony as one of the priorities of its policy.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated in his Message to the Oliy Majlis dated December 28, 2018: "Uzbekistan will always adhere to its traditions in the field of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, never deviating from this path. In our country, priority attention is paid to strengthening the atmosphere of mutual respect, friendship and harmony between representatives of different nationalities and religious confessions. This is our biggest asset, and we are all obliged to protect it like the apple of our eye." [1]

The fact that peace and tranquility is a great blessing has been reflected in Islamic sources. In particular, verse 13 of the Surah "Khujurat" reads: "O people! Indeed, We created you from a man and a woman and made you peoples and tribes so that you could know each other. Indeed, Muqarram with Allah is the most pious of you. Indeed, Allah is the Knower, the Knower." In this verse, Allah Almighty addresses all mankind with the words "O people" and says, "Your parents are one." That is, you are all descended from Adam and Eve. However, we have divided you into different nationalities, peoples, peoples and tribes. It follows from this that the division of people into different peoples, peoples, peoples and tribes took place according to the will of Allah.

The hadith also says that "peace and tranquility are two great blessings that many people are deprived of," that "whoever raises intrigues against us is not from Islam," that people are called to appreciate peace and live in harmony with each other.

Humanity at all stages of its development aspired, first of all, to peace and harmony. Because any progress is closely related to this. Therefore, peace in the country is an invaluable blessing, a pledge of great bliss and sustainable development. Peace is one of the main ideas that our Motherland tirelessly promotes in the world political arena.

Of course, peace cannot be achieved spontaneously or with the help of loud words, it must be maintained by consistent and decisive actions. To do this, it is necessary to simultaneously contemplate the processes taking place on the world political arena, to be able to foresee. One of the factors holding back the so-called blessing of peace is religious tolerance, interethnic harmony, which, perhaps, has already become a link in our national ideology.

All religions of the world are based on the ideas of goodness and call people to goodness, peace, mutual cooperation and friendship. We will not be mistaken if we say that Islam is the leader in this regard. The attention of our religion to issues of peace and tolerance is much greater, and these principles are an integral part of the faith of every Muslim.

"Say (O believers) that we believe in Allah and in the Book that was revealed to us, and in what was revealed to Abraham, Ishmael, Isaac, Jacob and the like, and in what was given to Moses and Jesus, and in what was given to all the prophets from their Lord. We do not separate them from each other, and we obey him." (Sura Bakara, verse 136).

According to the injunction set forth in this verse of Karim, every Muslim should believe in the prophets sent by Allah Almighty, just as Muhammad believes in Allah, just as he believes in the Quran in the scriptures sent down by Allah Almighty. If one of them does not believe or does not respect them, he will not remain a Muslim. So, tolerance first of all finds its expression in faith, which is the basis of our religion.

Allah loves the just", prescribing Muslim believers to maintain good relations with representatives of other nationalities and faiths, if they do not fight because of religious enmity and do not try to oppress and expel them from their country, emphasizing the need to be fair to them (norm). This judgment is a clear proof of how humane and peaceful Islam is, that Islam means tolerance (norm). This religion does not forbid anyone to do good and justice towards other religions.

In addition, in another verse of the Quran, Allah Almighty says: "...Eat from the inheritance of Allah and do not commit wickedness on earth!" (Surah "Bakara", verse 60) calls on all mankind to live in peace and tranquility, tolerating each other without causing harm.

Indeed, it is a sacred duty for all of us to educate the younger generation in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, making them brave, courageous, able to resist harmful influences and ideas alien to our mentality, in accordance with the ideas of interethnic and interfaith harmony and tolerance. With the participation of our mentors, who have contributed to the development of the country with their life experience, personal example, and their work, we must emphasize that further improvement of the atmosphere of spiritual, educational and moral relations in mahallas, secondary schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges, higher educational institutions, strengthening of legal propaganda of interethnic and interreligious harmony is the factor of peace, progress and prosperity must. These values, eternally sacred to our people, unite all forces and actions that have different opinions and views in society, thereby contributing to the strengthening of national unity.

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